

Label-free detection and profiling of individual solution-phase molecules

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The vast majority of chemistry and biology occurs in solution, where conformational dynamics and complexation underly behavior and function. Single-molecule techniques¹ are uniquely suited to resolving molecular diversity, and new label-free approaches are reshaping the power of single-molecule measurements. A label-free single-molecule method^{2–16} capable of revealing details of molecular conformation in solution^{17,18} would allow a new microscopic perspective of unprecedented detail. Here, we use the enhanced light-molecule interactions in high-finesse fiber-based Fabry – Pérot microcavities^{19–21} to detect individual biomolecules as small as 1.2 kDa, a ten-amino acid peptide, with signal-to-noise ratios >100, even as the molecules are unlabeled and freely diffusing in solution. Our method delivers 2D intensity and temporal profiles, enabling the distinction of sub-populations in mixed samples. Strikingly, we observe a linear relationship between passage time and molecular radius, unlocking the potential to gather crucial information about diffusion and solution-phase conformation. Furthermore, mixtures of biomolecule isomers of the

37 same molecular weight and composition but different conformation can also be
38 resolved. Detection is based on the creation of a novel molecular velocity filter
39 window and a dynamic thermal priming mechanism that leverage the interplay
40 between optical and thermal dynamics^{22,23} and Pound – Drever – Hall cavity locking to
41 reveal molecular motion even while suppressing environmental noise²⁴. New *in vitro*
42 ways of revealing molecular conformation, diversity, and dynamics can find broad
43 potential for applications in life and chemical sciences.

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46

47 **Introduction**

48 Tools to measure properties of individual molecules¹, including in heterogeneous
49 solutions, have become cornerstones of modern molecular and biomolecular research.
50 Nearly all single-molecule approaches use extrinsic labels, and while these labels provide
51 important contrast and specificity²⁵, label-free approaches that avoid arduous dye labeling
52 procedures which may perturb the native functionality of biomolecules^{26–28} are an
53 increasingly desirable alternative. Most single-molecule approaches, including all current
54 label-free methods, also rely on interaction with surfaces. While the presence of a surface
55 may be benign for many applications (such as molecular detection and mass determination),
56 for others, the measurement may bias detection towards sub-populations in mixed samples,
57 disrupt native molecular interactions, and alter dynamics and conformation relative to the
58 solution-phase properties^{18,29,30} (Supplementary Information). Here, we report a label-free
59 single-molecule technique that enables detection of small solution-phase biomolecules
60 (down to 1.2 kDa) with unprecedented signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and allows for resolution
61 of their diffusion behavior.

62 Many label-free single-molecule experiments emphasize molecular detection, whereby
63 the presence of a single copy of a specific molecule is perceived, typically via a surface-
64 bound, selective, tight binder like an antibody. Other approaches emphasize molecular
65 property assaying and extract information about the molecule, such as location, mass, or
66 spectroscopic profile. Property assays are typically incapable of unambiguously identifying
67 the molecule but can be applied generally, whereas molecular detectors can provide
68 selective identification, but only for a small subset of chosen molecules.

69 The gamut of label-free single-molecule technologies has grown substantially,
70 particularly across two modalities: interference-based and optical microcavity-enhanced
71 techniques. Interferometric measurements, which generally rely on interference between
72 elastically scattered light and a local oscillator, can operate as molecular detectors^{2,3} or
73 property assays capable of quantitatively determining position^{4–6} and mass⁷ of single

74 molecules. Dielectric optical microcavities provide enhanced light-matter interactions due to
75 high quality factor (Q) and low mode volume (V)^{8,9,31}. Microcavities have most commonly
76 been applied as molecular detectors, where plasmonic enhancement^{10–12}, optomechanical
77 coupling¹³, or a combination of frequency locking and computational noise suppression¹⁴
78 have enabled single-molecule detection via the reactive sensing mechanism³² where the
79 molecule introduces a shift in the resonance frequency. Selectivity is provided by a surface-
80 supported binder molecule, though the microcavity is sensitive to the presence of molecules
81 even without this step. Microcavities can also be used as single-particle property assays
82 providing details on size and shape^{33,34} or spectral information on electronic³⁵, plasmonic³⁶,
83 or vibrational properties³⁷, and dynamics³⁸. However, these approaches require target
84 molecules to be confined or surface-immobilized to allow signal integration and background
85 subtraction, be bound by a surface-supported selective binder, or require interaction with a
86 surface to couple to evanescent modes^{18,29}. Open-access Fabry – Pérót microcavities can
87 mitigate these concerns by operating in solution¹⁹ but have not reached the single-molecule
88 label-free regime. Advances include successful single-nanoparticle optical trapping in plano-
89 concave cavities³⁹ and, the recent demonstration of high-finesse fiber-based Fabry – Pérót
90 microcavities (FFPCs)²⁰ as highly effective sensors for detecting individual diffusing
91 solution-phase silica nanoparticles²¹. By monitoring frequency shift, formation of higher-
92 order spatial modes, and changes in transmission intensity, the nanoparticle position was
93 tracked and diffusion information was calculated²¹. Here, we take advantage of the open-
94 access geometry of FFPCs to achieve sensing of single, freely diffusing small biomolecules.
95 Our platform utilizes passive mechanical stabilization of FFPCs⁴⁰, a new dynamic thermal
96 priming mechanism, and active resonance frequency-stabilization as a novel form of
97 molecular velocity filtering, to achieve detection of a 10 amino-acid, 1.2 kDa solution-phase
98 single-protein with SNR of up to 123. This observation is achieved in the absence of external
99 surface-based signal multipliers like plasmonic enhancement and is the highest SNR
100 reported for label-free single-molecule sensing by a substantial margin. Most importantly, the
101 method operates without interaction with surfaces, allowing label-free interrogation of
102 solution-phase molecules and evaluation of molecular diffusion profiles, a carrier of key
103 information on conformation and binding⁴¹.

104

105 **Results**

106 The FFPC was assembled from two single-mode optical fibers with concave laser-ablated
107 end facets (Supplementary Fig. 1), which were subsequently coated with high-reflectivity
108 dielectric layers (Supplementary Information)²⁰. The fiber mirrors were aligned and affixed
109 laterally within a cut fused silica ferrule (Fig.1A, B) to increase the passive mechanical
110 stability⁴⁰. Optical modes were probed with static-frequency lasers over 660-760 nm while

111 monitoring reflection and transmission (Fig. 1A). The mirror separation was $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig.
112 1B), leading to Q-factors of $\sim 2 \times 10^6$ and mode volumes of $\sim 80 \mu\text{m}^3$ ²⁰. Continuous probing of
113 a single resonant mode was achieved via Pound – Drever – Hall (PDH) frequency locking
114 ^{24,42}, in which the cavity length was actively stabilized to a single frequency of the pump laser
115 (Fig. 1A). The input power into the cavity was $\sim 5 \mu\text{W}$ resulting in a circulating power of 5.5
116 mW. We demonstrate the ability to detect single label-free molecules by introducing samples
117 of varying mass (66-1.2 kDa) and radius (2.80-0.75 nm) into the FFPC. Protein samples
118 were prepared at pM concentrations such that the mean occupancy of the optical mode
119 volume was much less than one molecule. Intensity traces show high amplitude, correlated
120 signals, manifesting as a negative peak in transmission and a positive peak in reflection from
121 transient interactions between single diffusing protein molecules and the locked cavity mode
122 (Fig. 2A), resulting in extraordinarily high SNRs of up to 123 for the 10 amino-acid peptide
123 Myc-tag (Extended Data Fig. 1). Confirmation that signals originated from single-molecule
124 diffusion was achieved by showing water background measurements before introduction of
125 protein and after removal, during which no signal was observed (Supplementary Fig. 2);
126 demonstrating that detected events increased linearly with protein concentration (Extended
127 Data Fig. 2); and seeing Poisson statistics in arrival times (Extended Data Fig. 3). Without
128 relying on plasmonic enhancement mechanisms^{10–12,43}, surface proximity^{3,10–14,43}, or the
129 consequent conformational or chemical change of a surface-supported docking molecule
130 ^{14,43}, we demonstrate SNRs of up to 42-fold higher than existing label-free biomolecule
131 sensing techniques for molecules of comparable molecular weight (Supplementary Fig. 4)
132 ^{3,10–14}. Our approach also achieves a mass limit of detection ~ 25 -fold smaller than that of
133 direct mass photometry⁷, and when compared to mass photometry with machine learning,
134 achieves an ~ 8 -fold smaller limit of detection while offering $\sim 70\times$ higher SNR⁴⁴. Though the
135 data presented here is in pure water, proteins also give strong single-molecule signals in
136 their more native phosphate-buffered saline (Extended Data Fig. 4).

137 Each transit event comprises both temporal and intensity data. Most data were acquired
138 with a temporal resolution of $20 \mu\text{s}$, but $2 \mu\text{s}$ time resolution (500 kHz acquisition rate,
139 Extended Data Fig. 5) was also possible, suggesting the potential to capture even faster
140 dynamics.¹⁶ Plotting the distribution of temporal and intensity parameters provides a 2D
141 signal profile containing unique information on the molecular mass and diffusion (Fig. 2B).
142 Each protein molecule exhibited a distribution of temporal widths, identified from the full
143 width at half maximum (FWHM) of events that rise significantly above the noise, and
144 prominences, which increased with increasing protein molecular weight (Fig. 2B). A diversity
145 of widths is expected due to the stochasticity of Brownian motion. The downward shift to
146 lower prominences at shorter transient times is due to a combination of this same diversity of
147 molecular spatial paths and different intrinsic system response for smaller molecules. To

148 demonstrate the ability of this technique to move beyond detection, we explored the
149 potential for property assay by calculating the autocorrelation function of time traces
150 containing multiple individually-detected molecules to extract temporal information from the
151 data. Correlation spectroscopy is a ubiquitous tool across temporally sensitive biophysical
152 methods, such as fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (FCS) and dynamic light scattering,
153 aiming to extract ensemble diffusional and, therefore, size and mass information of
154 molecules^{41,45-49}. FCS typically suffers from significant Poisson noise due to the limited
155 number of detected fluorescence photons per molecule, a particular problem in versions that
156 rely on intrinsic fluorescence⁵⁰. In contrast, our microcavity-based readout is based on $>10^{12}$
157 of detected photons per second, even facilitating faster sampling (Extended Data Fig. 5).
158 Our method is also capable of quantifying diffusive behavior on molecules >50 times smaller
159 than other label-free single-molecule methods^{15,16}. The autocorrelation expectedly shows
160 dynamics on longer timescales for proteins of increasing mass (Fig. 3A). Importantly, the
161 autocorrelation times were consistently linear in proportion to the radius of the protein (Fig.
162 3B). This result confirms the versatility of this new single-molecule technique as a molecular
163 property assay, demonstrating the potential to extract meaningful molecular information,
164 including size and diffusional properties. Label-free methods of assessing molecular
165 dynamics can offer substantial impact in biophysical applications.

166
167 Having demonstrated single-molecule measurements of solution-phase, label-free
168 proteins, we next demonstrated the ability to resolve populations of simple binary mixtures.
169 Resolution of mixtures is vital for identifying diagnostic biomarkers, understanding disease
170 pathogenesis, and for elucidating biomolecule-biomolecule and biomolecule-drug
171 interactions. Techniques such as FCS, invaluable for inferring conformation, and
172 fluorescence polarization anisotropy, invaluable for ascertaining drug binding⁵¹, are
173 generally limited by the requirement for fluorescent labels. Ensemble label-free techniques
174 such as dynamic light-scattering can provide diffusive information of biomolecules, but
175 analysis is restricted by the high dependence of scattering on the molecular radius (r^6),
176 obscuring small particles among larger ones⁵², necessitating monodisperse samples for
177 quantitation⁷. Our approach produces 2D profiles that can act as molecular signatures (Fig.
178 2B) containing information about mass and diffusivity.

179 First, we investigated a mixture of aprotinin and Myc-tag, which have a 5.3 kDa mass
180 and 0.7 nm radius difference (Fig. 4A). The contour plot of the mixture is qualitatively similar
181 to the sum of the pure component distributions. Though these two populations would be
182 difficult to resolve considering only peak prominence, two distinct populations, a fast-moving
183 population with a mean event FWHM of 0.49 ± 0.15 ms and a broader, slow-moving

184 population with a mean event FWHM of 1.68 ± 1.37 ms, are clearly evident in the 2D
185 contour.

186 Moving beyond protein samples, we explored the resolution of bimolecular mixtures of
187 DNA isomers of identical mass (16.6 kDa) and composition, but differing sequence (Fig. 4B,
188 Extended Data Fig. 6, Supplementary Fig. 11): a DNA duplex (9 nm) and a Y-junction
189 structure (5 nm). Here, the two populations are clearly resolved in the 2D contour plot and
190 along either individual axis and both components are present throughout the experiment
191 (Extended Data Fig. 7). Spiking in known pure DNA samples identified the larger
192 prominence population as coming from the Y-junction (Extended Data Fig. 6). A ternary
193 mixture of three DNA Y-junctions of differing mass was also measured (Supplementary Fig.
194 12) and found to be at the limit of resolvability and is further discussed in the Supplementary
195 Information. As discussed below, the response of the FFPC to the molecular perturbation is
196 influenced by molecular properties as well as multiple dynamic cavity properties. The ability
197 to cleanly reveal the presence of two molecules of identical small mass but differing
198 conformation and diffusion behavior shows that this approach provides complementary
199 information that is not discernable from mass photometry.

200

201 **Discussion**

202 The detection of a single, freely moving, unlabeled small biomolecule with high SNR
203 requires a plausible mechanism whereby the small perturbation to the optical system can be
204 discerned. Our proposed mechanism begins with a refractive index change as the
205 biomolecule displaces water molecules of lower index in the microcavity (often referred to as
206 the “reactive mechanism”) ³². Resonance shifts of 1-49 kHz due to the altered optical path
207 length are estimated from the protein molecular weights (Supplementary Fig. 13). We note
208 that these shifts are $\sim 20\times$ greater at equivalent weights than estimates in whispering gallery
209 mode resonators ¹⁴ due to smaller mode volume and better spatial overlap between
210 molecule and optical mode in FFPCs (Supplementary Information). The ability to resolve
211 resonance shifts that are small compared to the cavity linewidth (~ 200 MHz) with such high
212 SNR is based on a combination of high passive stability, active low-frequency stabilization,
213 creation of a velocity discrimination window for molecular motion, and the use of dynamic
214 photothermal distortion of the resonance line shape. In water, the photothermal effects occur
215 due to absorption of some of the cavity circulating power, which alters the refractive index of
216 the medium via the thermo-optic coefficient.

217 The combination of mounting the FFPC in a glass ferrule and PDH locking provides
218 remarkable stability, suppressing mechanical and laser frequency noise to detector-limited
219 levels (Fig. 5A, Supplementary Fig. 14) ⁴⁰. Importantly, the PDH locking bandwidth (LBW)
220 only suppresses fluctuations (including molecular fluctuations) at temporal frequencies

221 below 5 kHz (Fig. 5A), where low-frequency mechanical fluctuations can introduce
222 substantial resonance shifts. This loop would also suppress perturbations produced by
223 larger, slow-moving molecules or particles, as the majority of their displacement would occur
224 within the PDH LBW (Fig. 5A). Importantly, small molecules undergoing Brownian motion,
225 albeit with smaller overall resonance shifts due to their reduced size, have a larger fraction
226 of their mean squared displacement power spectral density (MSDPSD)⁵³ outside the PDH
227 suppression window (Fig. 5A, Supplementary Fig. 15). Integration of the MSDPSD for the
228 smallest protein (Myc-tag, 0.75 nm) between the end of the locking bandwidth and the
229 photothermal bandwidth (discussed below) yields a root-mean-squared (RMS) displacement
230 of 93 nm (supplementary materials). This displacement is comparable to the ~250 nm
231 distance between the node and antinode of the cavity standing wave (Extended Data Fig. 8),
232 suggesting that the near full resonance shift from the diffusing molecule can be experienced
233 by the microcavity outside the PDH LBW. When the molecule diffuses back into the node,
234 the perturbation ceases, leading the system to exhibit a dependence on the molecular
235 diffusion constant (Fig. 3). Detection by shifting from node to antinode is distinct from the
236 operational mechanisms in evanescent detection modalities^{3,11,12,14,43}. Critically, a solution-
237 phase label-free apparatus allows this novel employment of PDH as a high-pass filter to
238 reduce mechanical noise while passing signals from fast-moving molecules (Fig. 5B), a key
239 difference compared to previous schemes.

240

241 The second element of our proposed mechanism relies on a photothermally induced
242 distortion of the resonance line shape (Fig. 5C) and a dynamic photothermal priming
243 mechanism, which amplifies small resonance shifts. FFPCs spatially confine relatively
244 intense optical fields, inducing on-resonance temperature changes inside the mode volume
245 media and consequent thermo-optic resonance shifts²². The presence of this thermal
246 nonlinearity clearly manifests as a broadened asymmetric cavity line shape upon active
247 scanning of the cavity length or wavelength (Fig. Extended Data Fig. 9)²³. This photothermal
248 nonlinearity arises from the mirror coatings and the aqueous medium and requires no light
249 absorption by the molecule itself^{32,54}. The photothermal bandwidth was determined
250 experimentally to be 21 kHz (Supplementary Fig. 16A), defining the upper limit of our
251 molecular observation window (Fig. 5B). In a non-PDH stabilized cavity, these photothermal
252 nonlinearities result in multiple distinct stable equilibria²². However, with PDH stabilization,
253 this nonlinearity can be used for additional signal amplification. Increasing the cavity
254 transmission by introducing an offset from the original, arbitrary locked position (Fig. 5C,
255 panel 1) results in the pump laser sitting at a frequency just lower than the cavity maximum
256 (Fig. 5C, panel 2). In this primed state, even the resonance shift of a diffusing molecule can
257 shift the cavity resonance to an unstable regime where the pump laser sits at a higher

258 frequency than the microcavity resonance (Fig. 5C, panel 3). Here, the shift triggers a
259 dynamic process by which the cavity cools faster than the LBW, resulting in further
260 resonance shift and more cooling, ultimately causing a substantial transmission decrease
261 (Fig. 5C, panel 4). Other molecule-induced mechanisms, such as scattering, may also
262 contribute to cavity cooling. After the molecule has diffused out of the antinode, the cavity
263 begins to warm, and eventually, the PDH recovers the initial locked position at a rate defined
264 by the LBW (Fig. 5C, panel 2). In the case of smaller perturbations (as with Myc-tag), the
265 cavity cools less, leading to the distribution of peak prominences. Evidence for this
266 mechanism can be found in controlled voltage pulses added to the output servo of the PDH,
267 providing internal perturbations that qualitatively mimic molecular passages (Extended Data
268 Fig. 10).

269 In summary, our proposed mechanism features molecules diffusing into the
270 microcavity, where their fast motion exceeds the PDH locking bandwidth. A hypersensitive
271 photothermally primed cavity, experiencing these fast molecular perturbations, rapidly cools,
272 leading to enhanced shift and massive signal. Both peak prominence and temporal width are
273 expected to be influenced by system parameters, including PDH LBW. However, while peak
274 prominence is a complex function of biomolecule molecular weight (and thus refractive
275 index) and diffusive parameters, the temporal width is expected to be dominated more
276 purely by diffusive parameters, leading to clear linear dependence (Fig. 3). Future work will
277 allow more quantitative information to be derived from peak prominence.

278

279 **Conclusion**

280 In the absence of surfaces, extrinsic labels, and plasmonic enhancers, this work has
281 demonstrated exceptional sensitivity in observing single, diffusing biomolecules, achieving
282 SNRs of >100 for a sub 1 nm peptide. Our approach leverages the open-access geometry of
283 micro-scale FFPCs to facilitate unimpeded biomolecule diffusion as well as maximize the
284 overlap between the biomolecules and the optical field. Our enhanced sensitivity relative to
285 other label-free techniques (Supplementary Fig. 4) originates in molecular velocity filtering
286 and photothermal priming, where two experimental challenges, fast molecular motion, and
287 thermal nonlinearity, are transformed into advantages. The resulting rich 2D
288 intensity/temporal data can be used to distinguish unique, identifying molecular signatures
289 and has the potential to provide quantitative mass and diffusional information.
290 Mass photometry, a new method that can provide quantitative mass information of unlabeled
291 biomolecules⁷, has been commercialized and widely adopted, showcasing the tremendous
292 possibilities of photonic single-molecule assays. Alternatively, our solution-phase FFPC-
293 based approach avoids surfaces while providing μs -scale dynamics, a substantially higher
294 sensitivity with ≤ 1 kDa detection limit, and 2D signal profiles that offer a path toward

295 distinguishing molecules based on conformation, which influences diffusion properties, as
296 well as just mass. FFPCs offer convenient fiber optic integration and molecules, after
297 passing through the FFPC, could be readily interrogated via mass photometry, making the
298 approaches truly complementary. Our approach also brings certain limitations at its current
299 level of maturity (Supplementary Information). The nonlinearity of the signal, originating in
300 the interplay between optical and thermal dynamics, imposes difficulties on the ability to
301 derive quantitative information from peak prominence and to resolve more complex
302 mixtures. Spatial resolution, so valuable in interferometric scattering, is largely absent in our
303 method. The need for pM-level sample concentrations will provide benefit in sample-limited
304 applications but also impose constraints on the ability to study bimolecular interactions.
305 Future work will ascertain which of these limitations are fundamental and which can be
306 circumvented. Simple experimental advances, such as suppression of external noise
307 sources, are expected to yield significant improvements, including the capability to detect
308 biomolecules smaller than 1 kDa. Optimization of measurement parameters using a
309 quantitative model will enable configuration of the bandwidth of the velocity filter to
310 selectively collect information from different diffusional populations. Our FFPC approach has
311 the potential to resolve rapid biomolecular conformation changes, elucidate self-assembly of
312 small molecules in complex samples, and provide routes to rapid screening of protein-
313 protein and protein-drug interactions. By being label-free and single-molecule, our method
314 can mitigate key experimental difficulties in FCS and dynamic light scattering, two widely
315 applied biophysical techniques. This straightforward and readily scalable apparatus will bring
316 numerous benefits to the fields of life and chemical sciences, such as trace analysis,
317 separation science, mechanistic insights, and clinical diagnostics.

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450
 451
 452 **Figures:**

Fig. 1. Measurement apparatus and resonance scan. **a** Simplified schematic of the FFPC-based single-molecule sensing instrumentation. Laser light (660-760 nm) of <1 MHz spectral width was transmitted through a linear polarizer (||) and half-wave plate

($\lambda/2$), selectively attenuated with a variable optical attenuator (VOA), and phase-modulated through a lithium niobate electro-optic modulator (EOM) driven by a 200 MHz voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO). Light was then coupled into the cavity via a fiber splitter, to enable collection of reflected light, and into an input optical fiber with transmitted intensity detected on a photodiode. PDH cavity-length stabilization, to maintain the cavity on resonance with the laser, was achieved using the frequency sidebands generated by the EOM driven by the VCO at 200 MHz. The error signal was generated by applying a low-pass filter to the mixed VCO reference and photodiode signals. This signal was then fed into the proportional-integral (PI) controller, which drives the ceramic piezo actuators to stabilize the cavity length to maintain resonance. Protein diffusion events were monitored in two channels on separate photodiodes, reflection and transmission. **b** Brightfield images of the FFPC optical fibers within the quartz ferrule. The fibers were affixed within the ferrule, forming a cavity 19.3 μm in length. **c** Wavelength scan used to determine the spectral linewidth of the cavity modes to be probed. The cavity finesse was 37450 in water.

453

454

Fig. 2. Signals from individual molecules. **a** Perturbations of the locked resonant cavity mode originating from single-protein diffusion events. The locked signal was monitored in both transmission and reflection, and the events manifested as a transient reduction of the transmitted signal intensity and an increase in the reflected intensity. **b** 2D plots and accompanied histograms of the extracted prominences and temporal widths of the reflected signals. The corresponding transmission data can be found in Supplementary Fig. 5.

455

Fig. 3. Diffusion information from single-molecule profiles. a Ensemble autocorrelation of several hundred single-protein diffusion events. **b** Relationship between mean autocorrelation time at an autocorrelation threshold of 40% (see Supplementary Fig. 9 for other thresholds) and the protein radius, showing a clear linear correlation. The linear regression does not intercept the origin (Supplementary Fig. 10), likely due to the finite length of the instrument response function. The error bars represent the standard error of the mean from multiple experiments within the same cavity.

456

Fig. 4. Resolution of mixtures. Contour plots of peak prominence versus temporal width and subsequent independent histograms for **a** a mixed protein sample of aprotinin (6.5

kDa, 1.45 nm) and Myc-tag (1.2 kDa, 0.75 nm) and **b** a mixed DNA structure sample of a duplex (16.6 kDa, 9 nm) and Y-junction (16.6 kDa, 5 nm), with multiple populations clearly resolved.

457

Fig. 5. Mechanism of cavity-enhanced single-molecule detection. **a** Plot showing frequency noise spectral density in water, LBW characterization, and mean-square-

displacement power spectral density (MSDPSD) of proteins, streptavidin, aprotinin, carbonic anhydrase, and Myc-tag. The noise spectral density of the locked cavity in water rapidly converges to the detector-limited noise (off-resonance noise), highlighting the high passive stability. The locking bandwidth of 5 kHz, defined by the 0 dB feedback gain crossing, governs the lower frequency limit of the velocity filter. The upper limit of the velocity filter is defined by the photothermal bandwidth (21 kHz). The molecular MSDPSD can be integrated within this filter bandwidth to determine the root-mean-square MSD **b** Cartoon illustrating the key processes and their frequency bandwidths. Noise below 5 kHz is suppressed by the PDH. The upper limit, defined by the LBW and the lower limit, defined by the photothermal bandwidth, determine the molecular diffusion velocity observation window. **C**) Schematic describing the mechanism of dynamic thermal priming (see text for details).

458

459

460

461 **Methods**

462 **Mirrored fiber production**

463 Copper-coated optical fiber with cladding diameter of 125 μm (IVG Fiber, Cu600)
464 was first etched using nitric acid (70%). This etching procedure removed the copper coating,
465 leaving a layer of carbon coating above the cladding. The carbon coating was removed with
466 a small amount of diamond paste on cloth; however, this step was removed for later fiber
467 production due to apparent contamination from the diamond paste. Fibers were flat-cleaved
468 ($<0.2\text{-}1^\circ$) using an automated cleaver (AFL Fujikura, CT-106)⁵⁵.

469 An 18 W CO₂ laser (Synrad, 48-1 KAM) generated the ablation laser beam, which
470 was guided and modified with polarizing, phase retarding, and other associated reflecting
471 and ZnSe focusing optics. An arbitrary waveform generator (Agilent, 33220A) controlled the
472 beam characteristics, and a digital optical power meter head (Thorlabs, S314C) with an
473 attached console (Thorlabs, PM100D) was used to measure the beam power. Optical fiber
474 substrates were mounted atop a fiber clamp (Thorlabs, HFF003), which rested upon a 3-axis
475 translation system (Thorlabs, MTS50-Z8; MTS50B-Z8; MTS50C-Z8), driven by a DC servo
476 motor controller (Thorlabs, KDC101) secured to a long-range single-axis translator for
477 inspection-ablation positioning (Thorlabs, LNR502(/M)) driven by a motor controller
478 (Thorlabs, BSC201). A CCD camera (Thorlabs, CS165MU) coupled to a long working-
479 distance microscope system (Navitar, 160-10) with a 20 \times magnification, 0.42 NA infinity
480 corrected objective (Mitutoyo, 378-804-3) illuminated by a 635 nm LED source (Thorlabs,
481 LEDD1B), was used to image the fiber position. Optimal ablation alignment was facilitated
482 by illuminating the fiber core with an optical fault finder (VFLTOOL, HGB30). The laser was

483 set to have a power of 0.28 W, and a shot time of 250 ms was controlled using a shutter in
484 front of the fiber. These shot parameters generated fibers with radii of curvature (ROC) at
485 the base of the ablation of 48 μm on average, and diameters, calculated by 2- σ of a
486 Gaussian fit to the ablation profile, of 21 μm on average (Supplementary Fig. 1).

487 The fibers were characterized with a ZYGO Interferometer. Two perpendicular slices
488 of the surface profile were analyzed. For calculating the ROC, the center of the ablation was
489 assumed to be the minimum. A polynomial fit was then performed, and stepwise derivatives
490 were averaged to calculate the ROC. For the diameter, Gaussian fitting was performed, and
491 the diameter was taken to be two standard deviations of the fit. The ellipticity of the ablation
492 was calculated by comparing both the ROC and the diameter values for the perpendicular
493 slices. The decentration of the ablation was also measured by coupling the fault finder
494 through the core of the fiber, which was then compared to the center of the ablation. The
495 decentration, ROC, diameter, and ellipticity were all used to determine the viability of a fiber.

496 The fiber substrates were coated commercially with wavelengths of maximum
497 reflectivity at either 635 nm (LASEROPTIK GmbH, Germany) or 635 and 780 nm
498 (LAYERTEC GmbH, Germany), in which alternating layers of Ta_2O_5 and SiO_2 were
499 deposited using ion beam sputtering (IBS). These generated distributed Bragg reflector
500 surfaces with transmission loss < 20 ppm, absorption loss < 10 ppm and scattering loss < 16
501 ppm.

502

503 **Ferrule-assembly Preparation**

504 The cavity bridge assembly was prepared using fused silica ferrules (VibroCom,
505 8×1.25×1.25 mm) with an inner bore of 131 μm , based on the procedure by Saavedra *et al.*
506 ⁴⁰. The glass ferrule was cleaned using an air plasma cleaner (Harrick Plasma, PDC-001-
507 HP) for 10 minutes. A thin layer of UV-curable glue (Dymax, 9037-F) was placed on two 150
508 V piezos (Thorlabs, PA4DG), which were aligned flat to the ferrule, ensuring that the
509 direction of translation was aligned with the long axis of the ferrule. The glue was then cured
510 using a UV light (Rolence Enterprise, Q6 UV). The assembly of ferrule and two piezos was
511 then affixed to a glass block, which was approximately 20×7×3 mm in dimension. This
512 assembly was then placed in an oven at 65-75 °C for 2-3 hours for additional curing of the
513 glue. After this, wires were soldered onto the piezos. Two cuts were made in the ferrule in
514 order to facilitate translation of the cavity length: one full-cut to separate the ferrule into two
515 parts, maximizing the cavity length translation, and one half-cut to preserve fiber alignment
516 along the inner bore. These cuts were made using diamond wire ($\text{\O} = 125 \mu\text{m}$) secured in a
517 jeweler's saw. The full-cut was made off center and the half-cut was made close to the
518 center of the ferrule to provide access to the cavity mode. After the full-cut, a small piece of

519 wire was placed in the bore to alert when the cut had reached the bore. During the cutting
520 process the glass dust was removed using canned air.

521 The ferrule was cleaned post-cutting by first running the ferrule under deionized
522 water for 5 minutes. Using a digital microscope to visualize, Millipore water was pipetted
523 through the bore of the ferrule and a piece of optical fiber was run through the bore to
524 remove any remaining glass dust. This process was repeated until no visible dust remained.
525 The ferrule was then rinsed under Millipore water and few drops of methanol ($\geq 99.9\%$)
526 were run through the ferrule, which was then dried thoroughly using a nitrogen gas line.

527

528 **Fiber cavity construction**

529 The previously described high reflectivity, mirror-coated optical fibers were spliced to
530 a connectorized patch cable (Thorlabs, P3-630Y-FC-2) using a fusion splicer (Fujikura,
531 FSM-100P). The fibers were aligned using a 6-axis piezo actuated stage (Thorlabs,
532 MAX602D). The input fiber was mounted to this stage using a tapered v-groove fiber holder
533 (Thorlabs, HFV002). The output fiber was held by a v-groove fiber holder secured to an XYZ
534 translation stage. To visually align the fibers, two cameras were aligned perpendicular to the
535 fiber axis. The top-down view used a CMOS camera (Thorlabs, DCC1545M) connected to a
536 zoom lens (Navitar, 1-50487). This imaging system was used for both alignment and to
537 estimate the distance between the fibers. The second perpendicular axis was visualized
538 using a digital microscope (Dino-Lite, AM4113ZT). Using both camera axes, the fibers were
539 then coarsely aligned to one another visually using the 6-axis stage. The next step was to
540 finely align the fibers by recording resonances. To do this, a ramp signal from a data
541 acquisition board (DAQ, NI, BNC-2120) was applied to a piezo controller (Thorlabs,
542 MDT693B), which drove the piezo aligned with the fiber axis. Laser light (635-760 nm) was
543 then injected into the input fiber and collected through the output fiber to an avalanche
544 photodiode (APD, Thorlabs, APD430A). Resonances were measured in transmission and
545 optimized by adjusting all parameters of the 6-axis stage. The cavity finesse was
546 characterized by either using a wavelength-tunable external cavity diode laser (Newport,
547 TLB-6704) or via an electro-optic phase-modulator (EOM, EOSpace, PM-0S5-10-PFA-PFA-
548 633, PM-0S5-01-PFA-PFA-765/781) by introducing sidebands at a known frequency (2.6
549 GHz) and the linewidth extracted via Lorentzian fitting. The mirror separation was $\sim 20\ \mu\text{m}$
550 (Fig. 1B), leading to Q-factors of $\sim 2 \times 10^6$ and mode volumes of $\sim 80\ \mu\text{m}^3$. The cavity finesse
551 ranged from 27,000-101,000 across multiple cavities (Supplementary Information) in
552 ambient conditions, reducing to 17,000-37,450 in water (due to increased absorption and
553 scattering losses and the higher refractive index of the medium, Fig. 1C).

554 The fibers were guided into the prepared ferrule using the top-down and
555 perpendicular views, and the cavity formed at the center of the half-cut. In order to secure

556 the fibers inside the ferrule, 2 μL of low-viscosity, UV-curable glue (Masterbond, UV16) was
 557 deposited onto each fiber in turn at the left entrance of the non-slotted ferrule and the right
 558 entrance of the slotted ferrule. The glue was drawn up the fiber using capillary action and
 559 was UV-cured (Rolence Enterprise, Q6 UV) after ~ 2 mm of travel into the ferrule. The piezos
 560 on the bridge were then attached to a piezo driver (nPoint, D.200) and driven to assess the
 561 resonances under constant cavity translation.

562

563 **Optical setup**

564 Experiments were performed on a custom-built setup (Supplementary Fig. 18). Either
 565 a single-frequency, continuous-wave diode laser (660 nm, Cobolt Flamenco, 90261, 300
 566 mW) of < 1 MHz linewidth or a tunable Ti-Saph cavity laser of < 100 kHz linewidth operating
 567 at a single frequency (760 or 780 nm, MSquared, SolsTiS) was passed through a linear
 568 polarizer and half wave-plate then fiber coupled into an electronic variable optical attenuator
 569 (Thorlabs, V600), then into an EOM (EOSpace, PM-0S5-10-PFA-PFA-633, PM-0S5-01-
 570 PFA-PFA-765/781) driven by a voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO, Mini-Circuits, ZX95-209-
 571 S+, 200 MHz). The light was then coupled into the input fiber of the cavity via a fiber-based
 572 beam splitter (Thorlabs, TW670R3A1), the power injected into the cavity was between 5-35
 573 μW . The circulating power (P_{circ}) was calculated using Equation 1:

$$P_{circ} = P_{in} T \eta \left(\frac{F^2}{\pi^2} \right) \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

574

$$\eta = |\langle \psi_{cav} | \psi_f \rangle|^2 \approx \frac{4d_m^2 d_f^2}{(d_m^2 + d_f^2)^2}$$

575 where P_{in} is the input power⁵⁶, η is the mode matching overlap integral⁵⁶, $d_m = \omega(z = L/2)$
 576 is the mode radius at fiber mirror (see eq. 10), d_f is the radius of the mode inside the SM
 577 fiber. T is the transmission factor of the mirror coating (transmission=10 ppm) and F is the
 578 cavity finesse. This expression is valid for all cavity systems influenced by absorption losses
 579⁵⁷. The remaining path of the splitter was collimated and then focused (Thorlabs, C560TME-
 580 B) onto the active area of an APD (Thorlabs, APD430A) enabling collection of reflected
 581 resonance light. The reflected signal voltage was sent to a DAQ board (NI, BNC-2120) and
 582 monitored using custom software. The transmitted light was collected through the output
 583 fiber of the cavity, collimated and focused (Thorlabs, C560TME-B) onto the active area of an
 584 APD (Thorlabs, APD430A). The transmitted signal voltage was sent to a diplexer (Mini-
 585 Circuits, ZDPLX-2150-S+), the low-frequency component (DC-10 MHz)⁵⁶ was then directed to
 586 the DAQ board (NI, BNC-2120) in order to monitor the transmitted signal. The high-
 587 frequency component (50-2150 MHz) was amplified and sent to a frequency mixer (Mini-
 588 Circuits, ZP-1MH-S+) in which it was multiplied by the sinusoidal signal of the VCO under a
 589 homodyne detection scheme. The resulting frequency components were low-pass filtered

590 (Mini-Circuits, SLP-1.9+) to extract the DC error-signal and directed to the error input of the
591 Pound – Drever – Hall lockbox (PDH, Vescent, D2-125). The locking feedback was supplied
592 to the piezos driving the cavity length via the servo output of the PDH lockbox.

593

594 **Hardware control and data collection software**

595 Experiments were performed using code written in-lab using Python 3 to handle both
596 instrument control and data collection. The code interfaced with a DAQ board (NI, BNC-
597 2120) and oscilloscope (Rigol, DS1104). For DAQ and oscilloscope connections, control
598 was established using the PyLabLib package published under the GPL-3.0 license
599 (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7324876). The control code was written together with a graphical
600 user interface (GUI) to streamline user control. The GUI and interactable elements of the
601 program use the Qt framework through PySide2 bindings under the GPLv2 license. A copy
602 of the control software is available for free use under the GPLv3 license at
603 https://github.com/FairhallAlex/ces_tools.

604

605 **Sample preparation**

606 Protein samples included tetrameric streptavidin (66 kDa, 2.80 nm)⁵⁸, carbonic
607 anhydrase (30 kDa, 2.10 nm)⁵⁹, aprotinin (6.5 kDa, 1.45 nm)⁶⁰ and c-Myc peptide, known
608 more commonly as Myc-tag (1.2 kDa, 0.75 nm)⁶¹. Lyophilized Streptavidin (MilliporeSigma,
609 189730), Carbonic anhydrase (MP Biomedicals, 0215387910), Aprotinin (MilliporeSigma,
610 A6106) and c-Myc peptide (MilliporeSigma, M2435) were dissolved to 1 mgml⁻¹ in phosphate
611 buffered saline (pH 7.4), aliquoted to appropriate volumes and stored at -20 °C. For
612 experimentation, samples were thawed on ice and diluted to the working concentration (0.25
613 pM-15 pM) in filtered (Ø= 20 nm, Whatman Anotop, WHA68091002) ultrapure Millipore
614 water (18 MΩ, pH 7). To ensure that the measurements would be at the single-molecule
615 level, the optical mode volume was calculated to host an average of 0.7 molecules at the
616 highest working concentration (15 pM).

617 DNA sequences for each construct were manually designed and validated by NUPACK
618 (www.nupack.org). Commercially available oligonucleotides (Integrated DNA Technologies,
619 **Error! Reference source not found.**) were purchased and used without purification. To
620 assemble each structure, corresponding DNA strands (5 µM) were mixed in folding buffer
621 (25 mM HEPES, 100 mM KCl, 10 mM MgCl₂, pH 7.4), then annealed in a PCR thermo-
622 cycler (Bio-Rad) by a linear cooling step from 95°C to 20°C over 2 hours (-0.1°C per 10
623 second). The products were further purified by a size-exclusion chromatography column
624 (Superdex 200 increase 10/300) on a ÄKTA pure system (Cytiva), to remove extra strand
625 and potential aggregates. The final concentration of each construct was determined by

626 Nanodrop (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Samples were stored at 4°C for less than 1 month
627 before use.

628

629 **Single-Molecule Diffusion Experiments**

630 Prior to introducing proteins, filtered (\varnothing = 20 nm, Whatman Anotop, WHA68091002)
631 MilliQ water (8 μ L) was added to the cavity. The input power in the cavity was controlled with
632 an applied voltage to the VOA (Thorlabs, V600A) to ensure consistent power was used for
633 all comparable experiments. The fundamental transmitted cavity mode was found under
634 active cavity length translation and PDH-locked with a proportional gain of -40 dB. The
635 locked position was tuned to the maximum possible transmission using the relative voltage
636 offset on the lockbox (Vescent, D2-125). If spurious events were detected during the lock,
637 the cavity was unlocked and cleaned under a flow of filtered MilliQ water and dried with N₂.
638 This process was repeated after protein experiments to ensure the cavity was clean. The
639 transmitted and reflected signals were monitored as a function of time at either 50 kHz or
640 500 kHz acquisition frequency. Intensity-time traces containing single-molecule events were
641 saved as .csv files every 30 seconds using the custom software described above. Water
642 control experiments were continued until 5 minutes of data in the absence of a spurious
643 signal was collected.

644 Solutions of proteins (either Streptavidin, Carbonic Anhydrase, Aprotinin, or Myc-tag,
645 0.2-15 pM, 8 μ L) or DNA (8 μ L, 10 pM) in filtered MilliQ water were introduced into the
646 cavity. The input power in the cavity was controlled with an applied voltage to the VOA to
647 ensure consistent power was used for all comparable experiments. The fundamental cavity
648 mode was found under active cavity length translation and PDH-locked with a proportional
649 gain of -40 dB. The transmitted and reflected signals were monitored as a function of time at
650 either 50 kHz or 500 kHz acquisition frequency. Intensity-time traces containing single-
651 molecule events were saved as .csv files every 30 seconds using the custom software
652 described above. It is important to ensure that the single-molecule signals in the
653 transmission geometry do not reach the noise floor of the detector as this will limit the
654 achievable dynamic range when studying molecules of varying mass/size. This can be
655 controlled by appropriately minimizing the input power and the relative voltage offset of the
656 PDH locking system.

657 To produce single-molecule traces in phosphate buffered saline (Extended Data Fig.
658 4) (PBS, 10 mM phosphate, 150 mM NaCl, pH 7.4), the PBS was filtered through protein
659 concentrators (ThermoFisher, 88152) using a centrifuge (Eppendorf, Minispin) at 12000 rpm
660 for 30 minutes. The buffer filtered through the column was collected and additionally filtered
661 (\varnothing = 20 nm, Whatman Anotop, WHA68091002). This cleaned buffer was then used to dilute
662 aprotinin to a concentration of 15 pM. These experiments were conducted on a PDH-locked

663 cavity in the same general manner as experiments in water. First, the cavity was cleaned
664 with water until no spurious events were detected in water. Then cleaned buffer was added,
665 again assuring no spurious events were detected. The aprotinin in PBS was then added to
666 the cavity, and data was collected. After this step, the cavity was cleaned with water. Buffer
667 control experiments under the same conditions were taken after the aprotinin experiments in
668 the cleaned microcavity to ensure the signal collected previously was due to single-molecule
669 diffusion events of the desired analyte (aprotinin).

670 Mixture experiments were conducted on a locked cavity in the same general manner
671 as the single biomolecule diffusion experiments. Experiments began by adding filtered (\varnothing =
672 20 nm, Whatman Anotop, WHA68091002) MilliQ water (8 μ L) and cleaning the cavity with
673 filtered MilliQ water, until 5 blank 30 second, consecutive transmission time traces could be
674 obtained. This same process was repeated after the set of DNA experiments to ensure the
675 cavity was clean and proper control data obtained.

676 DNA isomer spike experiments (Extended Data Fig. 6) were performed using a two
677 DNA isomers (**Error! Reference source not found.**): a duplex (16.6 kDa, 9 nm) and a Y-
678 junction (16.6 kDa, 9 nm). The duplex was diluted into filtered MilliQ water to a concentration
679 of 1 pM and the Y-junction to a concentration of 20 pM. Equal parts of these solutions were
680 then mixed for the initial mixture, yielding a concentration of 0.5 pM for the duplex and 10 pM
681 for the Y-junction.

682 After the proper blank controls were obtained, the initial mixture (8 μ L) was added to
683 the cavity. The cavity was then locked and data collected. After sufficient data was collected
684 for this condition, the cavity was unlocked, approximately 6 μ L of solution were removed
685 from the cavity, leaving solution behind, and the DNA duplex solution (6 μ L, 1 pM) were
686 added to the cavity. This addition defines the first "spike." The cavity was then relocked, and
687 data was taken for this next condition. Upon finishing data collection for the second
688 condition, the cavity was again unlocked and 6 μ L of solution were removed from the cavity,
689 and the DNA Y-junction (6 μ L, 20 pM) were added to the cavity. This was the second "spike"
690 to the cavity. The cavity was relocked and data collected for this third condition. Importantly,
691 at each step where solution is removed from the cavity, there is still solution from the prior
692 condition remaining.

693 DNA ternary mixture spike experiments (Supplementary Fig. 12) were performed
694 using three DNA Y junctions of varying mass: 9.2 kDa (2 nm), 16.6 kDa (4.5 nm), and 33
695 kDa (9 nm) (**Error! Reference source not found.**). The complexes were each diluted to 10
696 pM using filtered MilliQ water and then mixed in equal parts. This yielded an initial mixture of
697 each species having a concentration of 3.3 pM.

698 After the proper blank controls were obtained, 8 μL of the initial mixture was added to
699 the cavity. The cavity was then locked, and data collected. After sufficient data was collected
700 for this condition, the cavity was unlocked, approximately 6 μL of solution were removed
701 from the cavity, leaving solution behind, and 6 μL of the 9.2 kDa complex (3.3 pM) were
702 added to the cavity. This addition defines the first “spike”. The cavity was then relocked, and
703 data was taken for this next condition. Upon finishing data collection for the second
704 condition, the cavity was again unlocked and 6 μL of solution were removed from the cavity
705 the 16.6 kDa complex (6 μL , 3.3 pM) was added to the cavity. This was the second “spike” to
706 the cavity. The cavity was relocked and data collected for this third condition. For the final
707 condition, the cavity was unlocked and 6 μL of solution were removed from the cavity and
708 the 33 kDa complex (6 μL , 3.3 pM) was added to the cavity. This is the third “spike” to the
709 cavity and final condition, where the cavity was locked and data collected. Importantly, at
710 each step where solution is removed from the cavity, there is still solution from the prior
711 condition remaining.

712 **Signal Strengths and Temporal Samplings**

713 The prominence of the peaks differed between transmission and reflection detection
714 channels (Fig. 2B, Extended Data Fig. 1, Supplementary Fig. 5); this behavior arises from
715 the dispersion that is unique to FFPC cavities (Supplementary Fig. 6)⁵⁶. The mean temporal
716 widths of the events were unchanged at proportional gain values > -50 dB in the
717 proportional-integral (PI) control of the PDH system (Supplementary Fig. 7), where a higher
718 proportional gain value constitutes a higher locking bandwidth (LBW). Consequently,
719 experiments were conducted above this threshold at a LBW of ~ 5 kHz (Supplementary Fig.
720 8). Taken together, these data further confirm that these high amplitude signals originate
721 from the perturbation of the cavity mode volume by single diffusing proteins.

722 The extraordinarily high SNR of the single protein events, even down to the 10 amino-
723 acid peptide Myc-tag, highlights the potential to extend the dynamic range of applications to
724 both smaller molecules and higher acquisition rates. To demonstrate this, we measured
725 transient events of Myc-tag diffusion with 2 μs time resolution (500 kHz acquisition rate,
726 Extended Data Fig. 5). This high collection frequency facilitated the measurement of events
727 as narrow as 26 μs . With a 500 kHz collection frequency, even these high-speed events can
728 be sampled far beyond the minimum Nyquist requirement, highlighting the potential to study
729 kHz processes such as enzyme kinetics and conformational changes⁶² without sacrificing
730 SNR. Potentially higher sampling rates can be achieved with minimum contribution of photon
731 shot noise using faster analog electronics, as demonstrated recently,¹⁶ but the finite
732 photothermal bandwidth (see below) may limit the sensitivity at highly elevated sample rates.
733

734 **Locking bandwidth characterization**

735 The locking bandwidth (LBW) of the cavity was measured by adding a harmonic
736 perturbation (F_h) of known frequency and amplitude together with the error signal (e) using a
737 voltage adder to the PI input (Supplementary Fig. 17). To maintain a linear relationship
738 between the voltage of the error signal during locking and the frequency detuning of the
739 cavity, we optimized the amplitude of the perturbation to $0.2 \times$ the peak-to-peak amplitude of
740 the error signal. While the cavity was locked, we registered the sum of the perturbation
741 signal and the error signal for different frequencies of the perturbation signal. This allowed
742 us to measure the frequency at which the lock ceases to be effective at compensating for
743 the perturbation to the system to determine the 0 dB gain value and thus the LBW of ~ 5 kHz
744 (Supplementary Fig. 8, Figure 5A).

745

746 **Noise floor determination**

747 We measured the noise profile of the locked cavity from the error signal data. The
748 voltage amplitude of the error signal was converted to its corresponding cavity frequency
749 shift using the scanned error signal slope calibrated with the modulation sidebands at 2.6
750 GHz. From the calculated Fourier transform of the error signal, we extracted the RMS values
751 of the cavity resonance frequency shift. We performed this measurement for different
752 proportional gain settings where the maximum noise suppression was reached for the
753 maximum locking bandwidth at ~ 5 KHz. The noise floor was measured from the off-
754 resonance error signal. This value, as well as the cavity finesse and gain, determine the
755 LBW. We found effective noise suppression of external perturbations by the PDH-locking
756 loop at the level of the noise floor throughout the LBW. While the source of low frequency
757 noise is mainly due to ambient acoustic waves, mechanical waves that couple through the
758 cavity system via contact points to the optical table, higher frequency noise (above the LBW)
759 inherent to the electronic control systems is suppressed using a low pass passive filter
760 before the piezo connection. Mechanical resonances of the cavity are expected to appear at
761 frequencies above the LBW, however its magnitude is below the detector noise floor⁴⁰, at
762 the level of $10^3 \text{ HzHz}^{-1/2}$ (Supplementary Fig. 14). The high mechanical passive stability of
763 the cavity and the active PDH defines a frequency region where the cavity can be more
764 sensitive to internal perturbations as described in the main text.

765

766 **Voltage pulse experiments**

767 To demonstrate the mechanism described in the main text (Figure 5C), we induced
768 controlled perturbations to the locked cavity to mimic molecular perturbations to the cavity.
769 The passage of molecules into the cavity results in an increase in the average refractive
770 index, and a consequent decrease in frequency. This frequency decrease was mimicked by

771 transiently, slightly increasing the length of the cavity by applying a voltage pulse to the
772 piezo. Based on the measured duration of molecular transit events (Extended Data Fig. 1)
773 and their prominence, we initially selected the parameters of the pulse, including duration
774 and amplitude, to approximately induce similar detuning magnitudes and cavity transmission
775 profiles (Extended Data Fig. 10). Square pulse signals of 140 μ s-1 ms duration (Extended
776 Data Fig. 10) and 1 Hz repetition rate were produced to affect the cavity length while the
777 cavity was locked. The pulse produced by a function generator (Keysight, DSOX1204G) was
778 added to the servo output of the lockbox; this combined signal was then directed to the
779 piezos. The transmission signal of the locked cavity over time was recorded to ensure that
780 all perturbation events and pulse signals were correlated (Extended Data Fig. 10A). A small
781 reaction delay was seen due to the length of the cables that drive the piezo, the reaction
782 time of the electromechanics and the transmission signal to the DAQ card. The transmission
783 profile (Extended Data Fig. 10, blue trace) is the result of the step up voltage perturbation
784 (gray) which produced a steep reduction of the locked transmission signal due to the
785 photothermal effect (a), this was followed by a brief recovery to the locked state by the PI
786 feedback (b) followed by a second descent of the transmission signal as the step-up voltage
787 of the pulse shifts the cavity in the opposite direction (c), finally the PI control recovers the
788 locked state (d). When the pulse is generated, the resulting perturbation has a profile that
789 resembles the transmitted signal profiles of the cavity due to the molecular interaction,
790 (Figure 2A, Extended Data Fig. 1).

791

792 **Photothermal broadening and thermo-optic coefficient**

793 Optical microcavities with small mode volumes are susceptible to dynamic
794 photothermal nonlinearities that originate from the build-up of intense optical fields, causing
795 the temperature to increase in the cavity due to the absorption of this electromagnetic
796 energy by the cavity constituents. Coupling between the heat and cavity resonance
797 frequency can result in drift of resonance frequencies, and cooling cascades²².

798 These photothermal dynamics depend on the thermo-optic coefficient (dn/dT) of the
799 medium dominating the thermal dissipation. Increasing the temperature of a medium with a
800 negative dn/dT will result in a decrease in the refractive index, and a consequently lower
801 cavity resonance wavelength (high frequency). When the cavity length or laser frequency is
802 scanned, the resonance may drift to higher or lower wavelengths depending on the direction
803 of the scan and the cavity-laser detuning. When the cavity length is scanned to longer
804 lengths, the optimal resonance condition (Equation 2),

$$m\lambda = 2nL$$

Equation 2

805 where m is an integer, λ is the wavelength, n is the refractive index of the medium and L is
806 the cavity length, appears to change as n decreases, resulting in a need for still higher
807 lengths, and resulting in a distorted line shape, (Extended Data Fig. 9). This behavior is
808 expected in FFPCs when the medium is air and the thermal dissipation is dominated by the
809 mirror coatings, where an “effective” negative dn/dT ²³ due to thermal expansion results in a
810 shorter cavity length⁵⁶. A negative dn/dT is also expected when the medium is water⁶³. We
811 characterized the photothermal behavior in our FFPCs with water, by actively scanning the
812 cavity to increasing length and observing the direction of photothermal broadening in water
813 (Extended Data Fig. 9). A positive voltage gradient was applied to one of the piezos and
814 confirmation that the positive voltage corresponded to increasing cavity length was achieved
815 by tuning the wavelength of the pump laser and observing a shift of the resonance position
816 to higher voltages with a lower pump wavelength. The direction of the broadened resonance
817 was observed to be towards longer cavity lengths, thus lower wavelengths, as expected for
818 a system dominated by a medium with a negative thermo-optic coefficient.

819

820 **Photothermal bandwidth measurement**

821 Photothermal broadening of cavity lineshapes as a function of applied ramp speed
822 were recorded in order to quantify the photothermal bandwidth of the cavity in water
823 (Supplementary Fig. 16A). Resonances were recorded in transmission as a function of time
824 and the cavity length was tuned using a ramp signal applied to the piezos from a function
825 generator (Keysight, DSOX1204G). Phase modulated sidebands at a known frequency (2.6
826 GHz) were applied to be used as a frequency calibration marker to each trace. Initially, the
827 ramp frequency and amplitude were chosen to minimize the photothermal effects in the
828 cavity. This was determined by matching resonance lineshapes during both the increase and
829 decrease of ramp voltage. This trace was used to measure the linewidth of the cavity. From
830 there, the ramp speed was scanned and traces were recorded for both the increase and
831 decrease in ramp voltage components of the ramp signal.

832

833 **Data analysis for single-molecule diffusion and autocorrelation analyses**

834 Analysis of transmitted and reflected signals resulting from perturbation by single
835 biomolecules was performed with custom written code using Python 3. Raw data was
836 passed through a low-pass filter (1.2 kHz) using the SciPy.signal butter package.
837 Biomolecule and water control data collected at a single input power were first normalized to
838 the maximum (for reflection) or minimum (for transmission) signal intensity to enable all
839 signal peaks at a comparable power to be selected with a single threshold between 0-1.
840 Single events were identified and analyzed using the SciPy.signal find_peaks package.
841 Signal peaks were selected at a prominence threshold of 0.35. A temporal filter of 2 ms was

842 applied to ensure that only peaks separated in time by greater than 2 ms were selected.
843 Temporal widths were determined at the full width at half maximum of the event, and
844 prominences were determined as the vertical distance between the maximum of the peak
845 and the local background intensity.

846 Autocorrelation analysis was performed to quantify the temporal behavior of the
847 single-molecule events in the intensity-time traces with custom code written in Python 3. A
848 normalized function was generated by comparing time-shifted values to one another
849 (Equation 3):

$$G_k = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-k} (Y_i - \bar{Y})(Y_{i+k} - \bar{Y})}{\sum_{i=1}^{N-k} (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

850 where k is the number of time steps, N is the total number of points, Y_i is the intensity for a
851 specific time and \bar{Y} is the average intensity. Several 30 s intensity-time traces for proteins
852 diffusing in the locked cavity were concatenated. To ensure that the background was
853 approximately continuous between files, the minimum of each file was found and then
854 subtracted from every point. Events were identified with an intensity threshold 2.5 standard
855 deviations from the mean and used to generate an autocorrelation trace. The function
856 `sm.tsa.acf` from the package `statsmodels.api`, was used to generate the autocorrelation
857 function. These functions were plotted for the four different proteins (streptavidin, carbonic
858 anhydrase, aprotinin and Myc-tag, Figure 3A), and the values for different decay times were
859 extracted. The time to decay to 40% of the autocorrelation time is shown to be linear with
860 protein radius, Figure 3B. This linear trend was preserved for a large range of decay values
861 (Supplementary Fig. 9), demonstrating the robustness of the analysis. A copy of the analysis
862 software is available for free use under the GPLv3 license at
863 https://github.com/FairhallAlex/ces_tools.

864

865 **Data analysis for locking bandwidth determination**

866 To extract the effective LBW of the system, the Fourier transform of the signal was
867 measured at point S for each perturbation frequency (Supplementary Fig. 17). This Fourier
868 analysis allowed us to decompose the signal into its frequency components, revealing how
869 the system responds to different perturbation frequencies. The amplitudes at the
870 perturbation frequencies were extracted and normalized with respect to the input signal F_{in} .
871 This normalization process was crucial for comparing responses across different frequencies
872 and conditions. The normalized amplitudes were then converted to decibels (dB) to provide
873 a logarithmic scale that is commonly used in signal analysis. The result of the normalized
874 values is shown as a function of input frequency of the sine wave (Figure 5A, Supplementary
875 Fig. 8). The locking bandwidth was determined by identifying the frequency at which the
876 normalized amplitude crosses 0 dB. This point represents the boundary where the locking

877 system begins to lose its effectiveness in tracking and correcting for perturbations and was
878 determined to be ~ 5 kHz. It is noteworthy that at higher frequencies, the signal exhibited
879 amplification, attributed to a phase change in the control circuit referred to as the 'servo
880 bump'. This phenomenon is accounted for in the analysis. Additionally, at even higher
881 frequencies, the locking system had no discernible influence on the perturbation signal,
882 resulting in a consistent relative intensity at 0 dB.

883

884 **Signal-to-noise ratio determination**

885 The data traces were smoothed using various bin sizes to generate a moving
886 average, following:

$$F_{smoothed,i} = \frac{\sum_{j=i}^{i+(n-1)} F_{raw,j}}{n} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

887 where n is the bin size and F_i is the value of the function at index i . This smoothing
888 procedure was performed for a series of different bin sizes from $n=1$ to $n=250$
889 (Supplementary Fig 18). Following smoothing, the trace was normalized. This process of
890 smoothing the data was only performed for SNR calculations. To then calculate the signal-
891 to-noise ratio (SNR), the standard deviation of the background (σ_N) was taken from the
892 longest segment of background in the trace. The signal (S) was then calculated from the
893 amplitude of the peaks and the SNRs for the proteins measured in this paper
894 (Supplementary Fig. 4) were calculated by:

$$SNR = \frac{S}{\sigma_N} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

895 quantifying the SNR for each peak under each smoothing bin size. Giving the maximum
896 average SNR, a bin size of 190 was used for all datasets. With a 50 kHz data acquisition
897 rate and 190 point average, our SNR values can be considered to be over a 260 Hz
898 bandwidth.

899 For comparison with other techniques, where provided, SNR values were taken
900 directly from references ^{7,10,12,13,44}. For reference ³, data was extracted into a .csv from Figure
901 4a using WebPlotDigitizer. The SNR was then calculated by taking the maximum of the
902 signal and dividing it by the standard deviation of a region without signal. For reference ¹⁴,
903 the resonance shift was taken to be 5 am as a high estimate from Figure 5e and divided by
904 the reported noise level of 9.6×10^{-4} fm. For reference ¹¹, the standard deviation of the noise
905 was calculated by estimating 3σ from Figure 5b and dividing that by 3. The SNR was then
906 calculated using the mean reported value of 2.5 fm for the 8-mer and then dividing by the
907 previously calculated standard deviation.

908

909 **Data analysis for photothermal bandwidth determination**

910 To determine the photothermal bandwidth, the frequency shift of the photothermally
911 broadened peak was calculated for each corresponding ramp speed. The photothermally
912 broadened peak for each ramp speed had the larger distance between the left sideband and
913 the main peak, which was determined to be the interpeak distance. Using this information,
914 the frequency shift for each ramp speed was then calculated by calculating the difference
915 between the photothermally broadened interpeak distance and the photothermally narrowed
916 interpeak distance. The frequency shift as a function of the ramp speed (Extended Data Fig.
917 9) were then fitted to Equation 6²³.

$$\beta(x) = \frac{\beta_{ad}}{1 + x\tau} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

918 where β_{ad} and τ corresponded to the adiabatic thermal resonance shift and the thermal
919 reaction time constant respectively. $\beta(x)$ is the number of linewidths shifted and x is the
920 scan speed in linewidths/s. β_{ad} was calculated to be 8.28 linewidths and τ was calculated to
921 be 23.7 microseconds. Then using Equation 7:

$$f_{th} = \frac{1}{2\tau} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

922 τ was converted to f_{th} (21 kHz) which is the bandwidth for photothermal resonator length
923 stabilization.

924

925 **Data analysis for mixtures**

926 In the main manuscript, Figure 4 demonstrates the resolution of mixtures of proteins
927 and DNA isomers. This section discusses additional supporting experiments and further
928 analysis of mixtures.

929 For the DNA mixture, the identity of each isomer in the mixture was confirmed by
930 starting with a mixture (Figure 4B, Extended Data Fig. 6A), spiking in the Y-junction
931 (Extended Data Fig. 6B), then spiking in the duplex (Extended Data Fig. 6C). Scatter plot
932 versions of the contour plots in Figure 4 are shown in Supplementary Fig. 11. In a statistical
933 mixture of molecules, there should be no extended time periods where only one population
934 is observed, this is shown to be the case for both the protein and DNA mixtures (Extended
935 Data Fig. 8). Any mode wandering in the microcavity can be identified by a sudden shift of a
936 population to a different peak amplitude.

937 A 3-component DNA mixture of molecular weight 9.2 kDa, 16.6 kDa, and 33 kDa
938 (**Error! Reference source not found.**) was studied, starting with the mixture
939 (Supplementary Fig. 12A), and then independently spiking in each component. While the
940 smallest (Supplementary Fig. 12B) and largest (Supplementary Fig. 12D) components are
941 easily resolved (Supplementary Fig. 12ABCD), it is difficult to resolve the middle population
942 (Supplementary Fig. 12C). When the middle population is spiked, a population is

943 strengthened at (x,y)~(0.75 ms, 0.55 V). On the one hand, this population would not be
944 visible looking at the one-dimensional histograms (green and yellow histograms),
945 demonstrating the value of the 2D data. On the other hand, the location of this middle
946 population on the 2D histogram appears to be highly sensitive to system parameters. Thus,
947 resolving mixtures beyond binary mixtures appears to be at the edge of current feasibility.
948 This problem is likely a result of the nonlinear nature of the readout and is further
949 commented on in the “**Error! Reference source not found.**” sections below.

950

951 **Data availability**

952 A representative sample of the raw data supporting the findings of this work is openly
953 available on figshare at [insert link here], under the title of [title of the dataset], with the
954 following reference [ref/DOI]. The data is associated with Figures 2 and 3 in the main text.
955 The sample data is in .csv format and available without restrictions.

956

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981

982

983 **Acknowledgements**

984 This work was principally funded by the National Institute of Health (NIH, R01GM136981),
985 with resonator construction supported by the Q-NEXT Quantum Center, a U.S. Department
986 of Energy (DOE), Office of Science, National Quantum Information Science Research
987 Center, under Award Number DE-FOA-0002253. Additional instrumentation development
988 was supported by the Center for Molecular Quantum Transduction and the Energy Frontier
989 Research Center funded by DOE, Office of Science, BES under award DE-SC0021314, the
990 National Science Foundation (NSF) Quantum Leap Challenge Institute for Hybrid Quantum
991 Architectures and Networks, Award No. 2016136, and by Schmidt Futures. L.-M. N. was
992 partially funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
993 under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 886216. E.C. was funded by NIH
994 (MH061876 and NS097362). H.P. was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft
995 (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy – Cluster of
996 Excellence Matter and Light for Quantum Computing (ML4Q) EXC 2004/1 – 390534769. We
997 thank D. Hunger, T. Northup, and S. Vanga for help in initial fiber mirror and microcavity
998 fabrication, X. Huang and B. Cullinane for conversations on diffusion, M. Saffman for early
999 conversations on fiber microcavities, and B. Thompson and T. Drier for instrumentation
1000 development.

1001 **Author Contributions**

1002 R.H.G. and L.-M.N. conceptualized experiments. B.S., Y. P., A.J.B., along with L.T.
1003 performed the CO₂ fiber ablation with help from J.S., L.C.K., J.S.K., and H.P.. L.-M.N.,
1004 J.K.R., and S.W. constructed the cavities with help from C.H.V.. L.-M.N. and J.K.R.
1005 performed single-protein experiments and protein data analysis. D.S.-B. performed
1006 autocorrelation analysis. J.K.R. and L.-M.N. performed protein and DNA mixture
1007 experiments. C.S. and R.H.G. devised experiments to confirm the mechanism. C.S., J.K.R.
1008 and L.-M.N. performed locking bandwidth experiments, noise characterization and
1009 photothermal bandwidth quantification. C.S. and D.S.-B. performed simulations. A.J.F. and
1010 B.M. wrote the hardware code. Z.Z. and E.R.C. designed and Z.Z. purified DNA constructs.
1011 R.H.G., L.-M.N., C.S., J.K.R. and D.S.-B. wrote the manuscript.

1012

1013

1014 **Competing interests**

1015 R.H.G. and L.-M. N. have submitted PCT/US2023/079347, “Methods And Systems For
1016 Detecting Diffusing Single Particles”, filed November 10, 2023.

1017

1018 **Supplementary information**

1019 The online version contains supplementary material available at

1020

1021 **Correspondence and requests for materials** should be addressed to Randall Goldsmith.

1022 **Reprints and permissions information** is available at <http://www.nature.com/reprints>.

1023

1024

1025 **Extended Data Figure Legends:**

1026 **Extended Data Fig. 1 Zoomed in view of single-molecule signals.** Representative 44 ms
1027 traces of proteins Streptavidin, Carbonic Anhydrase, Aprotinin and Myc-tag perturbing the
1028 cavity mode in both transmission and reflection. Data collected in cavity one.

1029 **Extended Data Fig. 2 Linearity of peak count with concentration.** Number of detected
1030 peaks induced by Myc-tag as a function of the protein concentration. Error bars represent
1031 the standard deviation across datasets. This scaling demonstrates that the peaks are
1032 induced by interactions between biomolecules and the cavity-mode. Data collected in cavity
1033 two.

1034 **Extended Data Fig. 3 Poisson distribution of single-molecule signal arrival times.**

1035 Statistical analysis of the time intervals between single-molecule events for proteins
1036 Streptavidin, Carbonic anhydrase and Myc-tag. This analysis shows mono-exponential
1037 decays illustrating the underlying Poisson behavior of the experiment and providing
1038 evidence of single-molecule detection.

1039 **Extended Data Fig. 4 Detection of protein molecules in buffer.** Single-molecule
1040 transients of aprotinin are readily observed in PBS buffer, while the pure PBS buffer and
1041 pure water are devoid of single-molecule signals.

1042 **Extended Data Fig. 5 Detection of signals sampled at 500 kHz.** Single diffusion events of
1043 <1 nm protein, Myc-tag, are resolvable with 2 μ s temporal resolution. Representative single
1044 Myc-tag events collected with 500 kHz acquisition frequency. Data collected using cavity two
1045 at a concentration of 1 pM.

1046 **Extended Data Fig. 6 Histograms of detection events in mixtures.** Histograms showing
1047 extracted temporal widths and peak prominences of transmitted signals of **a** a binary DNA Y-
1048 junction:duplex mixture (Table S 1), **b** the mixture spiked with additional amounts of the pure
1049 Y-junction and **c**) the mixture spiked with additional amounts of pure duplex.

1050 **Extended Data Fig. 7 Staggered detection from mixtures.** Scatter plots of peak
1051 prominence vs peak number showing consistency of molecular populations throughout the

1052 duration of an experiment and minimal cavity mode wandering for **a** a binary mixture of
1053 Aprotinin and Myc-tag and **b** a binary mixture of a DNA Y-junction and duplex (Table S 1).

1054 **Extended Data Fig. 8 Simulation of microcavity resonant mode.** Simulated cavity mode
1055 given the mirror properties of cavity one (Table S 5) showing the normalized square of the
1056 electric field which is proportional to the total energy stored in the cavity. The zoomed image
1057 shows a particle localized in an antinode in the center of the optical mode.

1058 **Extended Data Fig. 9 Photothermally distorted cavity resonance scan.** Photothermal
1059 induced broadening of the transmitted cavity resonance in water, collected under cavity
1060 length tuning at two different pump wavelengths. The blue shift in pump wavelength shifts
1061 the resonance position to lower piezo ramp voltage, demonstrating that increased piezo
1062 ramp voltage corresponds to increased cavity length. Furthermore, the direction of the
1063 broadening is indicative of a negative thermo-optic coefficient of the medium as is expected
1064 in water. Despite the low circulating power (5.5 mW), photothermal broadening was
1065 apparent and leveraged to enable the high sensitivity of this measurement. The smaller
1066 peaks originate from polarization splitting due to the birefringence of the cavity mode. Data
1067 collected with cavity four.

1068 **Extended Data Fig. 10 Replication of single-molecule-like signals by pulsing the**
1069 **length of the microcavity.** **a** Transmitted intensity of locked cavity showing perturbations to
1070 the lock when voltage pulses are applied to the piezos at a frequency of 1 Hz. **b** The applied
1071 pulse, input-power and cavity locking parameters can be optimized to mimic signals induced
1072 by diffusing molecules. The step up voltage (gray) produced a steep reduction of the locked
1073 transmission signal due to the photothermal effect (a), this was followed by a brief recovery
1074 to the locked state by the PI feedback loop (b) followed by a second descent of the
1075 transmission signal as the step-up voltage of the pulse shifts the cavity in the opposite
1076 direction (c), finally the PI control recovers the locked state (d). Data collected with cavity
1077 four.
1078